

MANSHUR AND VASIQA IMPORTANT DOCUMENTS FOR STUDING ADMINISTRATIVE SYSTEM OF THE ASHTARKHANIES DYNASTY

Jumaniyoz Sangirov

Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan,
Doctoral student of the Institute of History
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12605138>

Among them, the most significant are the documents written in the territory under the rule of the Ashtarkhanies, which include manshur, and vasiqa, vaqfnoma, letters written mainly in Turkish and Persian languages. Among the documents, the most important type and the most important in clarifying the state administration are the manshurs¹. The reviewed manuscripts are kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies. Among them, the collection of documents stored under the name "Maktubot, munshoat va manshurot" under serial number 289 is the largest, and it contains manshurs written in Persian, written in Persian, and issued to officials and servants in the central and regional administration, belonging to the era of Imamkulikhan, Ubaydullahkhan and mainly Abulfaizkhan. Also, the manshurs issued by Subkhonkulikhan have been preserved in their original form².

In these manuscripts, it can be seen that there are duties and powers of a number of positions and titles that are not mentioned in the works. For example, Mirza Badi Divan also mentions the role of the alam mansab: "The narration accepted by the mufties on any issue becomes a decision (fatva) after it is sealed by the alam and has the right to be executed³. In the manshur written about the appointment of Khoja Shah Mufties to the position of alam of Bukhara region, information can be found that the post of alam was also given to the governorship of Somjin district of Bukhara region⁴. Or, Mirzo Badi devan and other researchers of the later period who relied on his information limit themselves to emphasizing that the task of the tugbegi was to lead the flag bearers⁵. In the manshur related to this position, it is noted that he was also given the governorship of the Komot district of Bukhara⁶. If Mirzo Badi writes⁷

¹ Manshur is an appointment document.

² Manshur on the appointment of Nizamiddin Khoja Yusuf as shakhulislam of Samarkand region and as sheikh and mutavalli of Khoja Ahror's tomb by Subkhonkulikhan (1636). SH AQF. 76th collection of documents, document 528; Manshur on the appointment of Farkhod Chuhraaqa as governor of Kufin region by Subkhonkulikhan (1688). SH AQF. Documents. 64th assembly. Document 180.

³ Mirakshah Munshi, Mulla Zahid Munshi. Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Khoja Shah mufti to the post of Bukhara region scholar. SH AQF. Manuscript number 289. Pages 110a 110b

⁴ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Khoja Shah mufti to the post of Bukhara region scholar. Pages 110a – 110b.

⁵ History of Balkh. C. 175

⁶ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment to the position of Tugbegi. Page 159a

that the duty of the chief mehtar (mehtari kalon) was to collect 1/4 of the ushur (dahyak) from the Muslims, half of the ushur from the non-Muslims, and the ushur of the military in cash, grain and other found things, he was assigned to this post. in the appointment letter, it is noted that the holder of this position also performed the sarkor (supervision) of "darulzarbi money exchange"⁸. The position of shaykhulislam in the central and regional administration controlled⁹ the determination of the prices of regional stone scales, daily food crops (in particular, grain, etc.) necessary for the population, judges, scholars, and scientists in the region. , teachers and other people should refer to him in all issues of the Sharia, and it is noted that Shaykhulislam supervised¹⁰ the activities of judges, heads of market control, imams, and muezzins.

Also, the notebooks, which must be kept by the officials who worked in the office, and the issues that must be recorded in them, are clearly indicated. For example, katta devon (devoni kalon) "oliy daftarxona (daftarxonayi oliy – دفترخانه عالی)"¹¹, *mushrif* "in'om daftari (daftari in'om – دفتر)"¹², *devoni daftari tanobona* "tonobona daftari (daftari tonobona – دفتر طنابانه)"¹³, *avorij devoni* "kirim daftari (daftari ovarij – دفتر اوارج)" va *tavjih devoni* "chiqim daftari (daftari tavjih – دفتر بروات دفتر)"¹⁴, *poygirnavis esa* "oliy barotlar daftari (daftari baravoti oliy – دفتر بروات دفتر)"¹⁵ controls can be clarified. In the manshur written by Subkhonkulikhan about his appointment to the governorship of the region, judges, muftis, pilgrims, sayyids, dignitaries, kakhudos he should recognize and obey the orders of the judges of that region, and he should fight for the prosperity of the region and the welfare of the people, he should secretly hand over taxes and grain to the central government in cash, and he should obey any

⁷ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. Manshur written about the appointment of Ubaidullah to the post of mehtari kalon. Pages 174a – 175a; A manshur written about the appointment of Mehtari Kalon. Pages 175a – 176a; Machma'-ul-arqam. Bargai. 156.

⁸ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Mulla Ibadullah to the position of mehtari kalon. Pages 175a – 176a.

⁹ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Mir Mohammad Sadiq Khoja to the sheikhulism of Kesh region. Pages 122a – 122b.

¹⁰ Manshur on the appointment of Nizamiddin Khoja Yusuf as shakhulislam of Samarkand province and as sheikh and mutavalli of Khoja Ahror's grave by Subhonquli Khan (1636). AQF. Documents. 76th assembly. Document 528.

¹¹ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Haji Talib to the position of head of the Bukhara region. Pages 164b – 165b.

¹² Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Mulla Shadi Divan to the office of the governor of Bukhara region. Pages 165b – 166a; Letter, munshoat and manshurot. Manshur was written about the appointment of Mirzo Ghani to the post of governor of Bukhara region. Pages 166b – 167a; Machma'-ul-arqam. Bargai. 154..

¹³ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. Manshur written about the appointment of the governor of Bukhara region to the position of Tonobona. Page 170b.

¹⁴ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. Mirzo Haidar is a manshur written about the appointment of the bookkeeper to the office of tavjih and avorij. Pages 173b – 174a..

¹⁵ Letter, munshoat and manshurot. A manshur written about the appointment of Mirzo Arif to the highest post of the poygirnavisi baravati daftar. Pages 171a – 171b.

summons issued by the central government. It is emphasized that the answer should be "I'm all ears" and it allows to further clarify the duties and powers of the governor.¹⁶

There is a lot of information about state administration in vasiqas¹⁷ In particular, they are kept today in the Institute of Oriental Studies¹⁸ National Archives of Uzbekistan¹⁹, Bukhara²⁰, Samarkand State United Historical-Architectural and Art Museum Reserve²¹. They contain valuable information about the administrative-territorial units of the country. In particular, in the will of 1630, all of Movarounnahr, Balkh, Badakhshan, Hisori Shodmon, Akhsi, Andijan, Tashkent and Turkestan²², subordinate to Imam Qulikhan, were mentioned, while in the will of 1657, Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Turkestan, Nasaf, Kesh, Hisori Shodmon were mentioned. , it is noted that Kolob and Balkh are under the control of Abdulaziz Khan.²³ In another charter from 1670-1671, the administrative-territorial units are shown more clearly: Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, Turkestan, Sayram, Akhsi, Andijan, Oratepa, Zomin, Khojand, Jizzakh, Balkh Badakhshan. It is emphasized that areas such as Chorjoi, Andhud, Chichektu, Maimana, Shiburgan, Nasaf and Hisori Shodmon were subject to Abdulaziz Khan²⁴. Most visas allow for further clarification of the administrative-territorial structure. In the wills of the dynasty period, Kesh region²⁵, Komot²⁶, Poyirud²⁷, Faroviz²⁸, Samijan²⁹ districts of Bukhara region³⁰, Ofarikent, Shavdor³¹, Urgut³² districts of Samarkand region are mentioned.

¹⁶ Manshur on the appointment of Farhad Chuhraoga as governor of Kufin region by Subhonquli Khan (1688). AQF. Documents. 64th assembly. Document 180.

¹⁷ A vasiqa is a formal contract for the purchase and sale of land.

¹⁸ SH AQF. Collection of documents 36, document 2; AQF. Collection of documents 36, document 1; AQF. Collection of documents 27, document 25; AQF. Collection of documents 4, document 2; AQF. Collection of documents 4, document 3; AQF. Collection of documents 4, document 4; AQF. Collection of documents 4, document 6; O.D. Chekhovych. Dokumenty k istorii agrarnykh otnasheniy v Bukharskom khanstve XVII - XIX centuries. Tashkent. 1954. S. 14-23, 41-46, 47-55, 56-64; 78 – 83, 87 – 89, 90 – 93, 94 – 97, 100 – 105, 106 – 109, 110 – 112, 113 – 115, 125 – 129, 136 – 139, 143 – 145, 147 – 150, 151 – 154, 155 – 158, 159 – 162, 163 – 167, 168 – 171, 172 – 178.

¹⁹ OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/1; OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/3; OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/4; OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1073/2.

²⁰ Thomas Welsford and Nouryaghdi Tashev. A catalogue of Arabic-script documents from the Samarqand museum. Samarqand. 2012. P. 34 – 35, 35 – 36.

²¹ A catalogue of Arabic-script documents from the Samarqand museum. (412) P. 273, 274.

²² Documents on the history of agrarian relations in the Bukhara Khanate of the 17th – 19th centuries. pp. 14 – 23.

²³ That work. Pages 47-55.

²⁴ That work. Pages 56 – 64.

²⁵ SH. Documents collection 4, documents 2, 3.

²⁶ SH. Documents collection 4, document 2.

²⁷ Documents on the history of agrarian relations in the Bukhara Khanate of the 17th – 19th centuries. pp. 41 – 46.

²⁸ SH. Document collection 4, document 3.

²⁹ SH. Collection of documents 27, document 25.

³⁰ OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/7

³¹ Documents on the history of agrarian relations in the Bukhara Khanate of the 17th – 19th centuries. pp. 78 – 83.

³² OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1073/2.

The information about such administrative-territorial units in the document is valuable in confirming some explanatory issues in the works. In particular, there is information in the works that Termiz was controlled through the Balkh region. In the charter dated 1670-1671, Choshtepa and Khorasan belonging to Shavdar district of Samarkand region are mentioned, and it is said that these areas were adjacent to the lands of Balkh region from the north³³. This fully confirms that Termiz, which is located between Samarkand and Balkh, was controlled through the Balkh region. Information about state administration can also be obtained from documents of the hukmnoma³⁴ judgment type. In particular, the considered rulings were mainly written in Persian, and today they are stored in the Institute of Oriental Studies³⁵, National Archives of Uzbekistan³⁶.

From the information in them, it is possible to get information about administrative-territorial units, their management positions and their tasks and powers. For example, from the decree of 1621, it is understood that the Samarkand region includes Anhor district³⁷, from the decree of 1611, it is stated that the governor of the region has the authority to own and dispose of land in his province³⁸. It allows to put forward the opinion that the population has fulfilled the tasks of attracting and supervising various duties (hashar, begor, laborer)³⁹.

As a conclusion, manshur and vasiqa important documents of the dynasty period have been preserved to this day in original, copies and collections. The information in them is to be found in some places in the works, the duties and powers of positions and titles in the central and regional administration, the administrative-territorial structure of the country, the changes that have occurred in them, and to fill them with information that is not found in them.

³³ Documents on the history of agrarian relations in the Bukhara Khanate of the 17th – 19th centuries. pp. 56 – 64.

³⁴ Hukmnoma is a document containing a judgment.

³⁵ Subhanquli Khan's verdict on the case of Mutavalliya of Mir Mulla Abdul Wahid and his son Mir Sayyid Hasan (1684). SH AQF. Collection of documents 63, document 171.

³⁶ OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/1; OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/5.

³⁷ OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/1.

³⁸ OZMA. I. Fund 323. List 2. Document 1197/5.

³⁹ Documents on the history of agrarian relations in the Bukhara Khanate of the 17th – 19th centuries, pp. 98 – 99.

